

ANALYSIS OF SELF-COMPACTING CONCRETE IN FRESH STATE WITH ADDITION OF MARBLE AND GRANITE BENEFICIATION RESIDUE

Flávia Silva Vieira, Universidade Federal de Campina Grande, Brasil, flaviasilvav18@gmail.com

Elisângela Pereira da Silva, Universidade Federal de Campina Grande, Brasil,
elisangellapereira@yahoo.com.br

Rodrigo Mendes Patrício Chagas, Universidade Federal de Campina Grande, Brasil,
rmpchagas@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

Self-compacting concrete (SCC) is a widely used composite owing to its ability of flowing without compaction, saving time and costs during concreting. In this study, powdered superplasticizer and marble and granite beneficiation residue (MGBR) were used as fines. Four mixtures were produced with different percentages of MGBR and their properties in the fresh state were assessed using the slump flow, J ring, L box, V funnel, and segregation column tests, defined by the Brazilian standard ABNT NBR 15823 (2017). All mixtures showed behaviors within the limits established by this standard for an structural concrete.

KEYWORDS

Self-compacting concrete; marble and granite beneficiation residue; fresh state properties.

INTRODUCTION

Brazil is one of the major producers of ornamental rocks worldwide, exporting 2,20 million tons in 2018 (Abriochas, 2018). However, ornamental rock beneficiation activities produce a significant amount of waste. Therefore, the use of the waste produced could contribute for the sustainable environment (Silva, 1998).

The beneficiation process of ornamental rocks consists of cutting the rock in plates followed by polishing. A mixture of water, steel grit, and lime is commonly used to facilitate the operation, producing a mud composed of these materials and rock waste. This fluid is collected in small channels and transferred to tanks until decantation of the powder, enabling the reuse of water. The solid material is removed and discarded in the environment (Xavier, 2019). Figure 1 shows an example of a small facility of marble and granite beneficiation and the steps to obtain the marble and granite beneficiation residue (MGBR).

a) Machine used for cutting

b) Collection of the mud produced

c) Decantation tank

Figure 1: Steps to obtain the MGBR

Several studies have focused on the analysis of self-compacting concrete (SCC) with addition of MGBR in different percentages. For instance, Barros (2008) analyzed the compressive strength and durability, Lisboa (2004) studied self-compacting, physical, and mechanical properties, and Xavier (2019) evaluated the microstructural properties of this type of concrete.

Some requirements must be met for a concrete to be considered as SCC: *fluidity* – the concrete must fill up all spaces in the formwork; *cohesion* – the concrete must maintain physical characteristics when passing through the rebars or other obstacles; *passing ability* – capacity to move around rebars without causing obstruction; and *resistance to segregation* – separation of aggregates must not occur during spreading (Tutikian & Dal Molin, 2021).

The materials used to produce SCC are basically the same as those used in conventional concrete. However, more fines are necessary. In general, mineral additions are utilized, requiring the use of superplasticizers to provide workability for the mixture (Gomes & Barros, 2009).

To verify whether the SCC meets the mentioned requirements, there are specific guidelines, such as the Brazilian standard ABNT NBR 15823 (2017), which stabilishes the following tests:

- Slump flow test: spreading and flow time are determined, and visual analysis of the concrete after spreading is performed to analyze the fluidity of SCC in free flow;
- J ring: in this test, the passing ability of the SCC in free flow through rebars is evaluated;
- L box: this test aims to evaluate the ability of the SCC in confined flow by using an L-shaped box with a vertical and horizontal section separated by a movable. The box has steel bars to simulate the concrete flowing through obstacles;
- V funnel: in this test, the viscosity of the SCC is analyzed by measuring the time required for the concrete to completely flow through the funnel;

- Segregation column: this test aims to determine the static segregation of SCC. It consists of measuring the mass of concrete in the top and bottom parts of a cylindrical specimen to analyze the concentration of coarse aggregate on the lower part.

In this work, SCC was produced using MGBR (from a local facility) as filler in three different percentages and addition of superplasticizer in powder. The fresh properties were assessed by slump flow, J ring, L box, V funnel, and segregation column tests.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

a) Materials

The materials used for the concrete production were: cement type III (high early strength); fine sand as fine aggregate, with maximum diameter $\phi_{\max} = 1.18$ mm and fineness modulus (FM) = 1.95; granitic crushed stone 0 as coarse aggregate; *Superflow* superplasticizer in percentages of 1.21%, 1.26%, 1.28%, and 1.30%; and addition of MGBR in percentages of 10%, 30%, and 50%.

b) Fresh concrete tests

All tests were conducted in the Materials Laboratory of the Federal University of Campina Grande – Campus Pombal. The tests were conducted in an open space during the day, in a place protected from the wind and direct sun radiation, to simulate usual conditions in a building site. The temperatures measured during the tests oscillated within 28 °C and 35 °C and the local humidity was in the range of 20% to 30%.

The following mixtures were produced: SCC-0, SCC-10, SCC-30, and SCC-50, in which the number indicates the percentage of MGBR used. The tests were conducted after the production of each mixture, and new mixtures were produced for each test to avoid changes in the rheological properties as a result of water loss by evaporation.

Slump flow test

Initially, the Abrams cone was filled and raised, the time for the concrete to reach the circular mark of 500 mm in diameter (T_{500}) was measured, and two diametral measurements, perpendicular to each other, were made. The final result was obtained by the arithmetic mean of these two values.

During the test, the visual stability index (VSI) was also verified by analyzing the distribution of aggregates in the mixture, distribution of mortar, and occurrence of exudation and/or segregation.

J Ring

Initially, the Abrams cone was filled with concrete without densification by the rod and raised such that the material could flow through the steel bars. When the concrete stopped flowing, two diameter measurements were taken, perpendicular to each other, and the arithmetic mean of these values was calculated. The test result was obtained by the difference between the spread mean diameters obtained in the slump and J ring tests.

L Box

In this test, the L-Box with three bars was used. The gate was opened filling the vertical portion of the box, allowing the concrete to flow. The passing ability was calculated by Eq. 1, as follows:

$$HP = \frac{H2}{H1} \quad \text{Eq. 1}$$

Where:

HP = passing ability;

$H1$ = the height of the concrete surface, measured from the bottom, at the end of the horizontal portion next to the vertical portion of the box [mm];

$H2$ = the height of the concrete surface, measured from the bottom, at the end of the horizontal portion next to the opposite face of the vertical portion of the box [mm].

V Funnel

The test consisted in filling the funnel with the SCC, gate after 10 s, and measuring the time for the concrete to completely flow (T_{10s}).

Segregation column

The test consisted of filling the segregation column with SCC, waiting for approximately 20 min, and removing portions of concrete from the top and bottom of the column using a trowel. Each portion of concrete was individually washed on a 4.75-mm mesh sieve to completely remove the mortar. In sequence, using a cloth, the coarse aggregates were superficially dried and weighed. These segregation resistance was calculated using Eq. 2, as follows:

$$SR = \frac{2 \times (m_B - m_T)}{m_B + m_T} \times 100 \quad \text{Eq. 2}$$

Onde:

SR = Segregation resistance of the concrete;

m_B = masse of coarse aggregate obtained in the concrete portion removed from the bottom [g];

m_T = masse of coarse aggregate obtained in the concrete portion removed from top of the column [g].

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Tests in fresh concrete

Slump flow test

Figure 2 shows the spreading obtained for each mixture and the corresponding results are presented in Table 1.

Figure 2: Spreading of mixtures in the slump flow test.

Table 1: Spreading, flow time (T_{500}), and VSI

Mixture	Spreading (mm)	Spreading classification according to ABNT NBR 15823-1 (2017)	T_{500} (s)	Viscosity classification according to ABNT NBR 15823-1 (2017)	VSI
SCC-0	625	SF1	2.50	VS2	VSI1
SCC-10	580	SF1	3.18	VS2	VSI1
SCC-30	660	SF2	4.00	VS2	VSI1
SCC-50	765	SF3	5.00	VS2	VSI1

The T_{500} test results indicated that the viscosity of the mixtures increased with the increase of the MGBR percentage, which also resulted in more time to flow. Regarding the viscosity, all mixtures were classified as class VS2, with good segregation resistance and able to provide a reduction in the pressure on the formwork.

All mixtures met the limits established by the standard ABNT NBR 15823-1 (2017). Moreover, the spreading became larger as the addition of MGBR increased except for SCC-10. This may be a result of the content of superplasticizer added, which was possibly not the ideal.

Regarding the spreading behaviour, mixtures SCC-0 and SCC-10 were classified as SF1, which means that their use is indicated only for unreinforced or slightly reinforced concrete structures, molded from the top with free flow, or small structures that do not require a long horizontal flow. Mixture SCC-30 was classified as SF2, being suitable for most of the current concrete applications, such as walls and columns. In addition, mixture SCC-50 was classified as SF3, which indicates that it is suitable for more complex and highly reinforced structures, as well as for different shapes. The maximum aggregate diameter smaller than 16 mm is also a favorable condition for use in these types of structure.

By the visual analysis of concrete, although mixtures SCC-30 and SCC-50 exhibited a slight exudation, no evidence of segregation was found in all mixtures, indicating that they were stable.

J-Ring test

Figure 3 shows the J ring test under free flow and Table 2 presents the corresponding results.

Figure 3: Passing ability in freeflow condition

Table 2: J-ring test results

Mixture	Passing ability (mm)	Passing ability class by the J ring test ABNT NBR 15823-1 (2017)
SCC-0	55.00	Out of the value range
SCC-10	5.00	PJ 1
SCC-30	55.00	Out of the value range
SCC-50	57.50	Out of the value range

The results in Table 2 indicate that only mixture SCC-10 met the limits established by ABNT NBR 15823-1 (2017), being classified as PJ1 and suitable for most current applications. The other mixtures exceeded the established limits and did not exhibit sufficient passing ability to flow under confined flow in formworks.

Although only mixture SCC-10 met the limits set by the Brazilian standard, all concretes exhibited constant flow, without flow obstruction or segregation, as observed in Figure 3.

L-Box test

Figure 4 shows the L-box apparatus used in the test to evaluate the passing ability of concrete and Table 3 presents the results obtained for each mixture.

Figure 4: Evaluation of passing ability under confined flow using the L-Box

Table 3: L-box test results

Mixture	Passing ability	Class according to ABNT NBR 15823-1 (2017)
SCC-0	0.83	PL 2
SCC-10	0.81	PL 2
SCC-30	0.87	PL 2
SCC-50	0.91	PL 2

From the data shown in Table 3, it is observed that all mixtures met the limits set by the Brazilian standard, being classified as PL2. This means that they are appropriated for most of the current concrete applications. The SCC-50 mixture exhibited the highest passing ability, close to 1.00, which could be due to the higher amount of superplasticizer used. In contrast, mixture SCC-10 exhibited the lowest passing ability.

V-Funnel test

Figure 5 shows the V-funnel apparatus during the test to determine the viscosity of concrete. The corresponding results are presented in Table 4.

Figure 5: V-Funnel test to determine concrete viscosity

Table 4: V-funnel test results

Mixture	Flow time (s)	Viscosity class – ABNT NBR 15823-1 (2017)
SCC-0	6 s	VF 1
SCC-10	5 s	VF 1
SCC-50	7 s	VF 1
SCC-50	9 s	VF 2

The results indicate that the flowing time increased with the increase of the MGBR percentage. Mixtures SCC-0, SCC-10, and SCC-30 were classified as VF1, thus requiring a higher control of segregation and exudation, as they exhibited low viscosity, flowing in less than 9 s. Although the standard establishes that segregation and exudation must not occur, both were observed during the tests for all mixtures. Only mixture SCC-50 was classified as VF2, being appropriate for most applications owing to its lower flowability and higher segregation resistance.

Segregation column test

Figure 6 shows the steps of the segregation column test, which was conducted to evaluate the segregation resistance of the mixtures. Table 5 presents the results obtained.

Figure 6: Determination of the segregation resistance using the segregation column

Table 5: Segregation resistance by the segregation column test.

Mixture	Segregation resistance (%)	Classification according to ABNT NBR 15823-1 (2017)
SCC-0	10.67	SR 2
SCC-10	17.89	SR 1
SCC-30	8.41	SR 2
SCC-50	5.31	SR 2

The results in Table 5 indicate that mixture SCC-10 was classified a SR1, being suitable for most applications, such as conventional structures with small thickness and low complexity, and without the need for a high control of segregation. The other mixtures were classified as SR 2, being appropriate for tall elements with high reinforcement (ABNT 15823-1, 2017).

Comparison between the results obtained in this study and those from similar studies

Table 6 presents the results of this study and those of similar studies for the mixture SCC-50, which has been commonly evaluated.

Table 6: Comparison of results obtained in this study and those from similar studies for SCC-50 in fresh concrete.

Tests	Samples			Usual limits			
	SCC-50 (This study)	SCC-50 (Xavier, 2019)	CR40 (Lisbôa, 2004)	Requirements ABNT NBR 15823-1 and EN 12350	Requirements ACI 237 R-07	Gomes and Barros (2009)	Tutikian and Dal Molin (2008)
Slump flow test (mm)	765	735	770	SF 1: 550–650 SF 2: 660–750 SF 3: 760–850	450–760	600–800	600–750
T ₅₀₀ (s)	5.00	1.90	0.81	VS 1: ≤ 2 VS 2: > 2	2–5	2–5	3–7
J ring (mm)	57	50	-	PJ 1: 025 PJ 2: 2550		0–10	0–10
L box	0.91	0.89	0.98	PL 1: ≥ 0.80 PL 2: ≥ 0.80	≥ 0.80	≥ 0.80	0.80–1.00
V funnel (s)	9	7	6	VF 1: < 9 VF 2: 925		6–15	6–12
Segregation column (%)	5.31			SR 1: ≤ 20 SR 2: ≤ 15	≤ 10	015	

Based on Table 6, it is observed that almost all results in this study were in agreement with requirements from standards and literature consulted, except for the J-Ring test result, which exceeded the established limits.

Moreover, in the three studies compared, a similar behaviour was observed in the slump flow test. In contrast, for the viscosity in the T₅₀₀ and V-Funnel tests, a lower flowability, and consequently higher viscosity, was obtained in the present study by both methods, compared to the results of the other studies.

As for the passing ability, evaluated by the J-Ring and L-Box tests, the result obtained in the J-ring test in this study was similar to that found by Xavier (2019). In the L-box test, all mixtures were classified as PL 2, as they had a passing ability higher than 0.80.

CONCLUSIONS

The results obtained indicated that the SCC with incorporation of MGBR as a filler exhibited a good performance in the fresh state, with an increase in viscosity, high cohesion, and less segregation.

The passing ability was evaluated in free and confined flow conditions. Although mixtures SCC-0, SCC-30, and SCC-50 did not meet the limits of passing ability in free flow (J-Ring test) set by the Brazilian standard, they exhibited satisfactory results in confined flow (L-Box test). This difference may be a result of the high temperature and low humidity during the tests. These factors may have caused loss of water from the concrete by evaporation in the closed environment of the L box, and maintained the concrete in a more fluid state in the free situation of the J ring.

Finally, considering the classifications established by the standards ABNT NBR 15823-1 (2017) and EN 1350 (2010), mixtures SCC-0 and SCC-10 are suitable for unreinforced or slightly reinforced concrete structures. Mixture SCC-30 can be used for common applications, with good surface finishing. Mixture SCC-50 concrete is suitable for vertical highly-reinforced structures, as it exhibits a high segregation resistance.

Therefore, the addition of RBMG to SCC can be a good alternative both to the disposal of this residue and to improve the SCC properties in fresh state.

CONFLICTS OF INTEREST

The authors have no conflicts of interest to declare.

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